

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By TOTAL DOMINATION IV

Dr. Henry Garrett ◦ Independent Researcher ◦ Department of Mathematics ◦ DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com ◦ Manhattan, NY, USA

1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\ & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \end{aligned}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$,

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and a Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to

understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Since there are more ways to get type results a Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. “values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, “Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, “values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, “super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV until Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, then it is officially called “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”, but otherwise, it is not Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Because of having Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV” and “neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an

intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV or the strongest Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV called Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and the strongest Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV called Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperI^{Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV}, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some

groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neurosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV or Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Strongly TOTAL

DOMINATION IV” and “neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, are specified in the sections “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV” and “Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”, “Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the

Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [1].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^{+}[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$^{-0} \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^{+}.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-0}, 1^{+}[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.5,p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

(ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

(iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $T'_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 2. TThe Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (4), there is no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 is a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 285
286
287
- On the Figure (5), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 288
289
- On the Figure (6), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 290
291
- On the Figure (7), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 292
293
- On the Figure (8), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 294
295

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 296
297
- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 298
299
- On the Figure (11), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 300
301
- On the Figure (12), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 302
303
- On the Figure (13), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 304
305
- On the Figure (14), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 306
307
- On the Figure (15), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 308
309
- On the Figure (16), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 310
311
- On the Figure (17), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 312
313
- On the Figure (18), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 314
315
- On the Figure (19), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 316
317

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-overpacked SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 318
319
- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 320
321
- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 322
323

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 324
(Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 325

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 326
327
328
329

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 330
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 331
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 332
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 333
334
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 335
336
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 337
338

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 339
340

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

(i) $1 \otimes x = x$;

(ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;

(iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$supp(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

(ii) $V = \{ (V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0 \}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

(iv) $E = \{ (E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0 \}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(vii) $\sum_i supp(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(viii) $\sum_{i'} supp(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up. 414
415
416

Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up. 417
418
419
420
421

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up. 422
423
424
425
426
427

Example 3.19. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is up. 428
429
430
431
432
433

Example 3.20. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is up. 434
435
436
437
438

Definition 3.21. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;

(iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;

(iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** .

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

(i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;

(ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;

(iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;

(iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

(ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5). 514
515
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6). 516
517
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7). 518
519

4 Main Resultant 520

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV). 521
522

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 523
524
525
526

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \forall V_a \text{ outside } B_s, \exists V_b \text{ inside } B_s, \exists E_c \text{ inside } E_{NSHG} : \\
 & (T(E), I(E), F(E)) = \text{maximum number of Neutrosophic strength} \\
 & \text{of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)} \\
 & V_i \text{ to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j,$

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8). 530

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=2,5}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 531
532
533
534
535

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints. 536

And 537

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices. 538

}|.

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9). 539

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 5-6}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 539

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 5-6}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j,$

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}}.

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 5-6}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside $B_s, \exists V_b$ inside $B_s, \exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength

of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j,$

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

}|.

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12). 557
558

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 5}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 559
560
561
562
563

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 564
565

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 566
567
568
569
570

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right.$$

$\forall V_a$ outside $B_s, \exists V_b$ inside $B_s, \exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength

of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

$\}.$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=2}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right.$$

$\forall V_a$ outside $B_s, \exists V_b$ inside $B_s, \exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength

of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j,$

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}}.

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right.$$

$\forall V_a$ outside $B_s, \exists V_b$ inside $B_s, \exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength

of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j,$

have Neutrosophic strength

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16). 587
588

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 589
590
591
592
593

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength

of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$,

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17). 594
595

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-4}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 596
597

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}}.

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-5}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

holds.

607

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E))$ = maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$,

have Neutrosophic strength

$$(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$$

such that

the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints.

And

the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices.

}|.

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

608

609

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-6}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds.

610

611

612

613

614

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

$\forall V_a$ outside B_s , $\exists V_b$ inside B_s , $\exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E))$ = maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$ such that the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints. And the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices. }|.

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20). 615
616

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperTOTAL DOMINATION IV criteria holds. 617
618
619
620
621

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\}$$

$\forall V_a$ outside $B_s, \exists V_b$ inside $B_s, \exists E_c$ inside E_{NSHG} :

$(T(E), I(E), F(E)) =$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$

is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $V_i, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{j-1}, E_{j-1}, V_j$, have Neutrosophic strength $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$

such that the values of the SuperHyperEdges are the maximum values of its endpoints. And the graph induced by B_s has no isolated vertices. }|.

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel coincides.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV number is as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV number is as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$P :$$

$$E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. \square

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set is as follows.

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly

TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.8. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV number is lower than as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV number is lower than as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel).*

- (i). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set.*
- (ii). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set.*

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

Proposition 5.12. (Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then $CENTER$ is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then $CENTER$ is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. \square

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (42) and the Table (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (42), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL

DOMINATION IV.

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 43. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (43), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (43) and the Table (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV.

9 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

Cancer is a neutrosophic disease, but the neutrosophic model is supposed to understand what is going on in this neutrosophic phenomenon. The special case of neutrosophic disease is considered and some parameters have been used as consequences of the model. Cells are subject to attack by the disease, but the movements of the cancer in the specific area is a matter of mind. Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer can help in finding

some Neutrosophic cures for this Neutrosophic disease. 850

In the following, several Neutrosophic stages are designed for this disease. 851

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer in long-term Neutrosophic performance. 852
853

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region is assigned by the Neutrosophic model (called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph) and the long Neutrosophic cycle of movement of cancer is identified by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. 854
855
856
857
858
859
860
861

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models that are well known and have names and some general Neutrosophic models. Cancer neutrosophic movements and effects in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find dominant neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV models or dominant sStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV models. 862
863
864
865
866
867
868
869

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations 870 871

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. 872

The SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”. 873
874
875

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?* 876
877

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV?* 878
879

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?* 880
881

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV?* 882
883
884

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStrongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, are there else?* 885
886
887

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?* 888
889

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?* 890
891

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title “Cancer Diagnosis”. To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV and Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called “Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV”, based on the connections of Cancer’s movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (23), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified,

Table 23. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV	
3. Neutrosophic Strongly TOTAL DOMINATION IV	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

pointed out and expressed.

12 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with

introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*" with ISO abbreviation "*Curr Trends Mass Comm*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments*" in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Treatments. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*A Research on Cancer's Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*" in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Recognition. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*" in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic

SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research" with ISO abbreviation "IJPAMR" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes" in Ref. [7] by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)" with ISO abbreviation "J Math Techniques Comput Math" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs" in Ref. [8] by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)" with ISO abbreviation "J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled "0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph" in Ref. [9] by Henry Garrett (2022), "0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs" in Ref. [10] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer's Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in Ref. [11] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer's Recognition" in Ref. [12] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer's Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in Ref. [13] by Henry Garrett (2022), "The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer's Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" in Ref. [14] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer's Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in Ref. [15] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in Ref. [16] by Henry Garrett (2022), "Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer's Circumstances Where Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in Ref. [17] by Henry Garrett (2022),

“(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [345]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [346]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [347]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [348]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [351]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in **Ref. [352]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [355]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [358]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [359]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in

Ref. [360] by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [361]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [362]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [363]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [374]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*” in **Ref. [375]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–375], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [376–551]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [552, 553].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [552]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [553]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “*Neutrosophic Duality*” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–375] alongside scientific research books at [376–551]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd ,in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [552, 553].

References

1. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot”, *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03).
2. Henry Garrett, “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05).
3. Henry Garrett, “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03).

4. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04). 1136
1137
1138
1139
5. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*”, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88). 1140
1141
1142
1143
6. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124). 1144
1145
1146
1147
7. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04) 1148
1149
1150
1151
8. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1152
1153
1154
1155
9. Garrett, Henry. “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. 1156
<https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1157
1158
1159
1160
1161
10. Garrett, Henry. “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. 1162
<https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1163
1164
1165
1166
11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1167
1168
1169
1170
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1171
1172
1173
1174
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1175
1176
1177
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and* 1178
1179
1180
1181

- Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1182
1183
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1184
1185
1186
1187
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1188
1189
1190
1191
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1192
1193
1194
1195
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1196
1197
1198
19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1199
1200
1201
1202
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1203
1204
1205
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1206
1207
1208
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1209
1210
1211
1212
23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1213
1214
1215
1216
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1217
1218
1219
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1220
1221
1222
1223
1224
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1225
1226
1227

27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1228
1229
1230
1231
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1232
1233
1234
1235
29. Henry Garrett, “Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1). 1236
1237
1238
1239
30. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14880269). 1240
1241
1242
31. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14862007). 1243
1244
1245
32. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14853973). 1246
1247
1248
33. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14847232). 1249
1250
1251
34. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14841803). 1252
1253
1254
35. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION IV”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14838245). 1255
1256
1257
36. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By TOTAL DOMINATION III”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14835115). 1258
1259
1260
37. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By TOTAL DOMINATION III”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14827829). 1261
1262
1263
38. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By TOTAL DOMINATION III”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14816635). 1264
1265
1266
39. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE DOMINATION III”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14807296). 1267
1268
1269
40. Henry Garrett, ”New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE DOMINATION III”, Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14796796). 1270
1271
1272

41. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION III", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14790988). 1273
1274
1275
42. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION III", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14787927). 1276
1277
1278
43. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION III", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14783549). 1279
1280
1281
44. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION III", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14775811). 1282
1283
1284
45. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By TOTAL DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14767980). 1285
1286
1287
46. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By TOTAL DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14758924). 1288
1289
1290
47. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By TOTAL DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14751658). 1291
1292
1293
48. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14743729). 1294
1295
1296
49. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14740792). 1297
1298
1299
50. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14736252). 1300
1301
1302
51. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14728447). 1303
1304
1305
52. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14722014). 1306
1307
1308
53. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION II", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14715180). 1309
1310
1311
54. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By TOTAL DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14708802). 1312
1313
1314
55. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By TOTAL DOMINATION I", ResearchGate 2025, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34901.33760). 1315
1316
1317

56. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By TOTAL DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14687820). 1318
1319
1320
57. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14680123). 1321
1322
1323
58. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14676029). 1324
1325
1326
59. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14662313). 1327
1328
1329
60. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14649067). 1330
1331
1332
61. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14649002). 1333
1334
1335
62. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION I", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14635630). 1336
1337
1338
63. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By TOTAL VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14633081). 1339
1340
1341
64. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By TOTAL VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14629965). 1342
1343
1344
65. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By TOTAL VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14624917). 1345
1346
1347
66. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14616539). 1348
1349
1350
67. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14609460). 1351
1352
1353
68. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14605277). 1354
1355
1356
69. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14601481). 1357
1358
1359
70. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14599113). 1360
1361
1362

71. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14593258). 1363
1364
1365
72. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14588231). 1366
1367
1368
73. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2025, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14584976). 1369
1370
1371
74. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14582614). 1372
1373
1374
75. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14577030). 1375
1376
1377
76. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14568932). 1378
1379
1380
77. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14566069). 1381
1382
1383
78. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14562607). 1384
1385
1386
1387
79. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14558506). 1388
1389
1390
1391
80. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14555481). 1392
1393
1394
1395
81. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14552432). 1396
1397
1398
82. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14547873). 1399
1400
1401
83. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14543895). 1402
1403
1404
1405

84. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14540759). 1406
1407
1408
85. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14536608). 1409
1410
1411
86. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527040). 1412
1413
1414
87. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14515147). 1415
1416
1417
88. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14507321). 1418
1419
1420
89. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By RESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14501230). 1421
1422
1423
90. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14477108). 1424
1425
1426
91. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14449513). 1427
1428
1429
92. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14261015). 1430
1431
1432
93. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14031032). 1433
1434
1435
94. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14019047). 1436
1437
1438
95. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13957693). 1439
1440
1441
96. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13909326). 1442
1443
1444
97. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13893734). 1445
1446
1447
98. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13890872). 1448
1449
1450

99. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13834065). 1451
1452
1453
100. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13826744). 1454
1455
1456
101. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13823150). 1457
1458
1459
102. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13748678). 1460
1461
1462
103. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13629264). 1463
1464
1465
104. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13618512). 1466
1467
1468
105. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13457634). 1469
1470
1471
106. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13447621). 1472
1473
1474
107. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13386125). 1475
1476
1477
108. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359880). 1478
1479
1480
109. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359103). 1481
1482
1483
110. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13329472). 1484
1485
1486
111. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13091499). 1487
1488
1489
112. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13134329). 1490
1491
1492
113. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13218489). 1493
1494
1495

114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786). 1496
1497
1498
115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339). 1499
1500
1501
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172). 1502
1503
1504
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424). 1505
1506
1507
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758). 1508
1509
1510
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919). 1511
1512
1513
120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1514
1515
1516
121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1517
1518
1519
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1520
1521
1522
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1523
1524
1525
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1526
1527
1528
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1529
1530
1531
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1532
1533
1534
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1535
1536
1537
128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1538
1539
1540

129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1541
1542
1543
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1544
1545
1546
131. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1547
1548
1549
132. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1550
1551
1552
133. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1553
1554
1555
134. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1556
1557
1558
135. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1559
1560
1561
136. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1562
1563
1564
137. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1565
1566
1567
138. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1568
1569
1570
139. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1571
1572
1573
140. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1574
1575
1576
141. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1577
1578
1579
142. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1580
1581
1582
143. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1583
1584
1585

144. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1586
1587
1588
1589
145. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1590
1591
1592
1593
146. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1594
1595
1596
1597
147. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1598
1599
1600
1601
148. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1602
1603
1604
1605
149. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1606
1607
1608
1609
150. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1610
1611
1612
151. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1613
1614
1615
152. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1616
1617
1618
1619
153. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1620
1621
1622
154. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1623
1624
1625
155. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1626
1627
1628
156. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1629
1630
1631

157. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1632
1633
1634
1635
158. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1636
1637
1638
1639
159. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1640
1641
1642
1643
160. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1644
1645
1646
1647
161. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1648
1649
1650
1651
162. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1652
1653
1654
1655
163. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1656
1657
1658
1659
164. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1660
1661
1662
1663
165. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1664
1665
1666
1667
166. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1668
1669
1670
167. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1671
1672
1673
168. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1674
1675
1676

169. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1677
1678
1679
170. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1680
1681
1682
171. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1683
1684
1685
172. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1686
1687
1688
173. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1689
1690
1691
174. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1692
1693
1694
175. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1695
1696
1697
176. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1698
1699
1700
177. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1701
1702
1703
178. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1704
1705
1706
179. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1707
1708
1709
180. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1710
1711
1712
181. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1713
1714
1715
182. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1716
1717
1718
183. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1719
1720
1721

184. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1722
1723
1724
185. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1725
1726
1727
186. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1728
1729
1730
187. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1731
1732
1733
188. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1734
1735
1736
189. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1737
1738
1739
190. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1740
1741
1742
191. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1743
1744
1745
192. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1746
1747
1748
193. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1749
1750
1751
194. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1752
1753
1754
195. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1755
1756
1757
196. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1758
1759
1760
197. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1761
1762
1763
198. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1764
1765
1766

199. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1767
1768
1769
200. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1770
1771
1772
201. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1773
1774
1775
202. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1776
1777
1778
203. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1779
1780
1781
204. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1782
1783
1784
205. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1785
1786
1787
206. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1788
1789
1790
207. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1791
1792
1793
1794
208. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1795
1796
1797
1798
209. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1799
1800
1801
210. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1802
1803
1804
211. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1805
1806
1807
212. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1808
1809
1810

213. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1811
1812
1813
214. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1814
1815
1816
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1817
1818
1819
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1820
1821
1822
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1823
1824
1825
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1826
1827
1828
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1829
1830
1831
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1832
1833
1834
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1835
1836
1837
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1838
1839
1840
223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1841
1842
1843
224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1844
1845
1846
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1847
1848
1849
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1850
1851
1852
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1853
1854
1855

228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1856
1857
1858
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1859
1860
1861
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1862
1863
1864
231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1865
1866
1867
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1868
1869
1870
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1871
1872
1873
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1874
1875
1876
1877
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1878
1879
1880
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1881
1882
1883
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1884
1885
1886
238. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1887
1888
1889
239. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1890
1891
1892
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1893
1894
1895
241. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1896
1897
1898

242. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1899
1900
1901
243. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1902
1903
1904
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1905
1906
1907
245. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1908
1909
1910
246. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1911
1912
1913
247. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1914
1915
1916
248. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1917
1918
1919
249. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1920
1921
1922
250. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1923
1924
1925
251. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1926
1927
1928
252. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1929
1930
1931
253. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1932
1933
1934
254. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1935
1936
1937
255. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1938
1939
1940
256. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1941
1942
1943

257. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1944
1945
1946
258. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1947
1948
1949
259. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1950
1951
1952
260. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1953
1954
1955
261. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1956
1957
1958
262. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1959
1960
1961
263. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1962
1963
1964
264. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1965
1966
1967
265. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1968
1969
1970
266. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1971
1972
1973
267. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1974
1975
1976
268. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1977
1978
1979
269. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1980
1981
1982
270. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1983
1984
1985
271. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1986
1987
1988

272. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1989
1990
1991
273. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1992
1993
1994
274. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1995
1996
1997
275. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1998
1999
2000
276. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 2001
2002
2003
277. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 2004
2005
2006
278. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 2007
2008
2009
279. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 2010
2011
2012
280. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 2013
2014
2015
281. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 2016
2017
2018
282. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 2019
2020
2021
283. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 2022
2023
2024
284. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 2025
2026
2027
285. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 2028
2029
2030
286. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 2031
2032
2033

287. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 2034
2035
2036
288. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 2037
2038
2039
289. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 2040
2041
2042
290. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 2043
2044
2045
291. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 2046
2047
2048
292. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 2049
2050
2051
293. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 2052
2053
2054
294. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 2055
2056
2057
295. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 2058
2059
2060
296. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 2061
2062
2063
297. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 2064
2065
2066
298. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 2067
2068
2069
299. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 2070
2071
2072
300. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 2073
2074
2075
301. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 2076
2077
2078

302. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047).
2079
2080
2081
303. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446).
2082
2083
2084
304. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961).
2085
2086
2087
305. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361).
2088
2089
2090
306. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125).
2091
2092
2093
307. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321).
2094
2095
2096
308. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441).
2097
2098
2099
309. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367).
2100
2101
2102
310. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048).
2103
2104
2105
311. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286).
2106
2107
2108
312. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602).
2109
2110
2111
313. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285).
2112
2113
2114
314. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569).
2115
2116
2117
315. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206).
2118
2119
2120
316. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320).
2121
2122
2123

317. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 2124
2125
2126
318. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 2127
2128
2129
319. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 2130
2131
2132
320. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 2133
2134
2135
321. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 2136
2137
2138
322. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 2139
2140
2141
2142
323. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 2143
2144
2145
2146
324. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 2147
2148
2149
2150
325. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 2151
2152
2153
2154
326. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 2155
2156
2157
2158
327. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 2159
2160
2161
2162
328. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 2163
2164
2165
2166
329. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 2167
2168
2169

330. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 2170
2171
2172
331. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 2173
2174
2175
332. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 2176
2177
2178
2179
333. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 2180
2181
2182
2183
334. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 2184
2185
2186
2187
2188
335. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 2189
2190
2191
2192
2193
336. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 2194
2195
2196
2197
337. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 2198
2199
2200
338. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 2201
2202
2203
2204
339. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 2205
2206
2207
2208
340. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 2209
2210
2211
341. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and* 2212
2213
2214
2215

- Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 2216
2217
342. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 2218
2219
2220
2221
343. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 2222
2223
2224
2225
344. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 2226
2227
2228
2229
345. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 2230
2231
2232
346. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 2233
2234
2235
2236
347. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2237
2238
2239
2240
348. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 2241
2242
2243
2244
349. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2245
2246
2247
2248
350. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2249
2250
2251
351. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 2252
2253
2254
352. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 2255
2256
2257
2258

353. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2259
2260
2261
2262
354. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 2263
2264
2265
2266
355. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 2267
2268
2269
2270
356. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 2271
2272
2273
357. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 2274
2275
2276
358. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 2277
2278
2279
359. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 2280
2281
2282
360. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2283
2284
2285
361. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2286
2287
2288
2289
362. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2290
2291
2292
363. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2293
2294
2295
2296
364. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2297
2298
2299
365. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2300
2301
2302

366. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2303-2307
367. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2308-2312
368. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2313-2315
369. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2316-2318
370. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2319-2322
371. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2323-2326
372. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2327-2330
373. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2331-2334
374. Henry Garrett, “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2335-2337
375. Henry Garrett, “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2338-2341
376. Henry Garrett, ”DOUBLE DOMINATION IV In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14885246). 2342-2343
377. Henry Garrett, ”DOMINATION IV In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14853961). 2344-2345
378. Henry Garrett, ”TOTAL DOMINATION III In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14838214). 2346-2347

- 379. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLE DOMINATION III In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14816626). 2348
2349
- 380. Henry Garrett, "DOMINATION III In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14790978). 2350
2351
- 381. Henry Garrett, "TOTAL DOMINATION II In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14775524). 2352
2353
- 382. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLE DOMINATION II In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14751646). 2354
2355
- 383. Henry Garrett, "DOMINATION II In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14736045). 2356
2357
- 384. Henry Garrett, "TOTAL DOMINATION I In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14715170). 2358
2359
- 385. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLE DOMINATION I In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14687792). 2360
2361
- 386. Henry Garrett, "DOMINATION I In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14635622). 2362
2363
- 387. Henry Garrett, "TOTAL VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14635622). 2364
2365
- 388. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLE VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14616656). 2366
2367
- 389. Henry Garrett, "VERTEX-EDGE DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14601608). 2368
2369
- 390. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLE DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14588523). 2370
2371
- 391. Henry Garrett, "PAIRED-DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14577256). 2372
2373
- 392. Henry Garrett, "EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14562725). 2374
2375
2376
- 393. Henry Garrett, "STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14544008). 2377
2378
- 394. Henry Garrett, "DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527741). 2379
2380
- 395. Henry Garrett, "RESTRAINED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14497269). 2381
2382
- 396. Henry Garrett, "Dom-forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14175736). 2383
2384
- 397. Henry Garrett, "Diamond search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13600433). 2385
2386
- 398. Henry Garrett, "Triangle-free search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13594674). 2387
2388

399. Henry Garrett, "Diamond search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13525750). 2389
2390
400. Henry Garrett, "Triangle-free search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13512157). 2391
2392
401. Henry Garrett, "Edge Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13376543). 2393
2394
402. Henry Garrett, "Vertex Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13294466). 2395
2396
403. Henry Garrett, "Burning Number In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12797511). 2397
2398
404. Henry Garrett, "Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570). 2399
2400
405. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785). 2401
2402
406. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087). 2403
2404
407. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996). 2405
2406
408. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821). 2407
2408
409. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118). 2409
2410
410. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2411
2412
411. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2413
2414
412. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2415
2416
413. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2417
2418
414. Henry Garrett, "Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2419
2420
415. Henry Garrett, "Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2421
2422
416. Henry Garrett, "Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2423
2424
417. Henry Garrett, "Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2425
2426
418. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2427
2428

419. Henry Garrett, "Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2429
2430
420. Henry Garrett, "Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2431
2432
421. Henry Garrett, "Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2433
2434
422. Henry Garrett, "SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2435
2436
423. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2437
2438
424. Henry Garrett, "Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2439
2440
425. Henry Garrett, "Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2441
2442
426. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2443
2444
427. Henry Garrett, "Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2445
2446
428. Henry Garrett, "Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2447
2448
429. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2449
2450
430. Henry Garrett, "Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2451
2452
431. Henry Garrett, "Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2453
2454
432. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2455
2456
433. Henry Garrett, "Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2457
2458
434. Henry Garrett, "Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2459
2460
435. Henry Garrett, "United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2461
2462
436. Henry Garrett, "Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2463
2464
437. Henry Garrett, "Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2465
2466
438. Henry Garrett, "Collections of Math II". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2467
2468

439. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2469
2470
440. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2471
2472
441. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2473
2474
442. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2475
2476
443. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2477
2478
444. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2479
2480
445. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2481
2482
446. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2483
2484
447. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2485
2486
448. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2487
2488
449. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2489
2490
450. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2491
2492
451. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2493
2494
452. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2495
2496
453. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2497
2498
454. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2499
2500
455. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2501
2502
456. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2503
2504
457. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2505
2506
458. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2507
2508

459. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2509
2510
460. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2511
2512
461. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2513
2514
462. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2515
2516
463. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2517
2518
464. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2519
2520
465. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2521
2522
466. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2523
2524
467. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2525
2526
468. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2527
2528
469. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2529
2530
470. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2531
2532
471. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2533
2534
472. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2535
2536
473. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2537
2538
474. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2539
2540
475. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2541
2542
476. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2543
2544
477. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2545
2546
478. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2547
2548

479. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2549
2550
480. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2551
2552
481. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2553
2554
482. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2555
2556
483. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2557
2558
484. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2559
2560
485. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2561
2562
486. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2563
2564
487. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2565
2566
488. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2567
2568
489. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2569
2570
490. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2571
2572
491. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2573
2574
492. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2575
2576
493. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2577
2578
494. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2579
2580
495. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2581
2582
496. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2583
2584
497. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2585
2586
498. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2587
2588

499. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2589
2590

500. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2591
2592

501. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2593
2594

502. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2595
2596

503. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2597
2598

504. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2599
2600

505. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2601
2602

506. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2603
2604

507. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2605
2606

508. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2607
2608

509. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2609
2610

510. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2611
2612

511. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2613
2614

512. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2615
2616

513. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2617
2618

514. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2619
2620

515. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2621
2622

516. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2623
2624

517. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2625
2626

518. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2627
2628

519. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2629
2630
520. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2631
2632
521. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2633
2634
522. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2635
2636
523. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2637
2638
524. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2639
2640
525. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2641
2642
526. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2643
2644
527. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2645
2646
528. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2647
2648
529. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2649
2650
530. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2651
2652
531. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2653
2654
532. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2655
2656
533. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2657
2658
534. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2659
2660
535. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2661
2662
536. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2663
2664
537. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2665
2666
538. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2667
2668

539. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2669
2670
540. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2671
2672
541. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2673
2674
542. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2675
2676
543. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2677
2678
544. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2679
2680
545. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2681
2682
546. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2683
2684
547. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2685
2686
548. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2687
2688
549. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2689
2690
550. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2691
2692
551. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2693
2694
552. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2695
2696
553. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2697
2698